

EFFECT OF THE MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM TECHNIQUE ON ENDOMETRIAL POLYPS: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a therapeutic technique developed by Isaac Goiz Durán which uses medium-intensity magnets placed on specific points of the body. It is a system for diagnosing dysfunctional magnetic fields, treating and preventing diseases. Endometrial Polyps (EP) are sessile or pedunculated masses that occur in the uterine cavity, which can be solitary or multiple, and vary from millimeters to centimeters. Some researchers suggest that EP is generally benign but it has the potential to progress to neoplasia at any age, with or without symptoms. This study is a case report developed in Cosmópolis city, São Paulo state, Brazil. The volunteer is a 48-year-old woman who lives in the city of Arthur Nogueira, São Paulo. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of

MB application on EP observed via Transvaginal Pelvic Ultrasound before and after treatment. The promising research investment is valid because it is a non-invasive, painless, easy-to-apply, and low-cost technique, with various possibilities for application in various pathologies. The research participant showed complete remission of EP after treatment with MB. It is concluded that this technique may be an alternative for the treatment of the disease and should be investigated in larger trials regarding its efficacy in treating and preventing the malignancy of EP. In the future, there may be the possibility of MB becoming a complementary technique to conventional medicine in public health care.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Static Magnetic Fields; Magnets; Endometrial Polyp; Prevention; Gynecology; Integrative Treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Endometrial polyps (EP) are abnormal growths of endometrial glands (NIJKANG et al., 2019). They can be solitary or multiple, with various sizes (from millimeters to centimeters) (RACKOW; JORGENSEN; TAYLOR, 2011) filling the entire uterine cavity (SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019). EP are composed of endometrial glands and stroma with some differences based on types: (1) functional, which presents endometrial tissues similar to the adjacent endometrium; (2) non-functional, where an immature type of endometrium is observed (“out-of-phase”) with irregular glands poorly responsive to progesterone (NOGUEIRA, 2005).

Histologically, the EP presents fibrous stroma and blood vessels with thick walls typical of the basal layer that often accompany their major axis, being lined by normal, atrophic, or other altered glandular epithelium beyond simple hyperplasia (NOGUEIRA, 2005; LŐRINCZ et al., 2019). They are usually benign but can progress to neoplasia at any age with or without symptoms (RACKOW; JORGENSEN; TAYLOR, 2011; SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019).

Although the etiology and pathogenesis of EP have not been fully elucidated (ELFAYOMY; SOLIMAN, 2015; SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019) it has been related to hormonal disorders such as anovulation, luteal phase abnormalities, excess in

estrogen production, or hormone therapy (LŐRINCZ et al., 2019; NIJKANG et al., 2019).

The actual incidence of EP seems to be underestimated but current literature points out that 10-30% of worldwide prevalence (KAC et al., 2020). Its prevalence for malignant lesions ranges from 0.5% to 3% (LASMAR et al., 2020). Polyps affect women of all ages, usually between 40 and 60 years old (LASMAR et al., 2020; SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019).

EP may be detected by transvaginal ultrasound, hysterosonography, hysterosalpingography, diagnostic hysteroscopy, endometrial biopsy, and uterine curettage (ELFAYOMY; SOLIMAN, 2015; LŐRINCZ et al., 2019; LASMAR et al., 2020). Patients with polyps can be asymptomatic. When symptomatic, it may present with irregular bleeding, heavy or prolonged menstrual periods, or postmenopausal bleeding, endometritis, pain, and possible infertility, often associated with tamoxifen treatment (KAC et al., 2020; SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019; VROOM et al., 2019).

EP is usually benign but, in some cases, the histopathological analysis indicates atypical hyperplasia or cancer. Therefore, many authors recommend surgical removal (KAC et al., 2020; SOLJAČIĆ VRANEŠ et al., 2019). Others propose more conservative treatments such as polypectomy in symptomatic patients or in postmenopausal women (LŐRINCZ et al., 2019). Okamura et al. (2021) observed that EP smaller than 10 mm may not require immediate surgical treatment since 15% may regress in 2-3 months. In parallel, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) may be another complementary therapeutic technique used for the benefit of patients with polyps.

MB is a therapeutic technique developed by the physician Isaac Goiz Durán which uses static magnetic fields generated by medium-intensity magnets (from 1,000 to 7,000 gauss) under specific points of the body. The tool was developed in 1988 together with the first Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) discovery (called "Thymus-Rectum" BMP) becoming a system of dysfunctional biomagnetic-electric field

diagnosis for disease treatment and prevention (DURÁN, 2003; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023).

The first scientist to study the effects of magnetism on the living organism was Albert Roy Davis during the 1930 who considered the bioelectric nature of cells in various tissues and organs. Davis' studies indicated that magnetic fields increase cellular biological activity. The muscle relaxation may be triggered when this tissue is exposed to the north pole of a magnet. Conversely, the activating and strengthening muscle effect may be reached after exposure to the south pole (DAVIS JR., 1974; PERSON, 2016).

Decades later, the scientist Walter C Rawls Jr. patented the method of scanning and diagnosing some diseases based on experiments about the influence of the magnet in biological systems. In the 1970s, a NASA scientist Richard Broeringmeyer noticed that astronauts, when returning from space trips, presented a shortening of the right hemibody, neurological alterations, and weaknesses in the immune system (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; PERSON, 2016).

Since then, the asymmetry of the limbs decreased progressively when astronauts underwent the treatment. However, this phenomenon occurred as they moved away from the magnetic field of the planet (BROERINGMEYER, 1991). Broeringmeyer concludes that when astronauts stay for long periods outside of magnetic fields they need to be treated with their own magnetic nature (DURÁN, 2008).

Based on these studies, Isaac Goiz Durán developed some hypotheses about biomagnetic poles. Durán claims that disordered poles may be generated in the body caused by temperature variations or pH imbalances. In this condition, a vibrational and energetic resonance phenomenon may be established. Consequently, the BMP is formed in a biochemical structure composed by two charges with opposite polarities: one acid and the other alkaline (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023).

Thus, the dysfunctional magnetic fields may be subjectively identified inside living beings as well as their correction through other static magnetic fields

generated by medium-intensity magnets. At its core, Goiz firstly named this technique as Medicinal Biomagnetism (DURÁN, 2008). In 2020, it was updated to Medicinal Biomagnetism in order to not generate conflicts with aspects of conventional medicine (BOSSA, 2023).

PBM is generally formed from energetic and metabolic dysfunctions of an organism. Ionic charges become polarized due to changes in the bioelectricity of the organism caused by factors such as temperature changes, intoxication, poor nutrition, and stress. This leads to an imbalance in local or systemic pH, which makes the individual susceptible to the action of pathogenic microorganisms (DURÁN, 2003; DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023).

Diseases are present in the biomagnetic poles that support the charges of biochemical elements and sustain the presence of viruses, fungi, bacteria, parasites, archaea, dysfunctions, or intoxications. Therefore, MB consists of balancing the bioelectricity of the organism bringing conditions to reach the Normal Energy Level (NEL) (DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023). NEL is the set of conditions necessary for the normal functioning of all chemical reactions in organisms. To maintain the NEL it is necessary to observe some basic principles: pH, universal law of charges, resonance, entropy, and symbiosis (MARTÍNEZ, 2018; BOSSA *et al.*, 2023).

According to Durán (2008), magnets must be applied to the corresponding anatomical location when identifying the PBM. Then, the structure that maintains tissue dysfunctions of pH and/or supports pathogenic microorganisms is disrupted. Afterward, toxins are released and the immune system is naturally activated returning homeostasis to the organism.

There are few scientific research and publications on the effect of MB. The literature on its possible efficacy in the treatment of tumors is still scarce (DAMYANOV, 2019a, 2019b; MARTINI *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, more studies on this technique are necessary. In addition, MB is an accessible technique that provides several possibilities of applicability in various pathologies. Thus, a more consolidated literature on case reports can support more robust studies. The aim

of this study was to observe the application effect of the MB technique on EP. In addition, another aim is to quantify the number of MB sessions required and verify the BMP used in the technique sessions, comparing the results of Transvaginal Pelvic Ultrasound exams before and after treatment with BMP.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is a descriptive, cross-sectional, retrospective study conducted at a Medicinal Biomagnetism clinic in Cosmópolis city, São Paulo, Brazil. This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee on August 27, 2022 (N° 5.589.702). The research participant signed the Informed Consent Form (ICF) prior to the start of the study. The participant was a 48-year-old white female living in the city of Arthur Nogueira, São Paulo State. She was a mother of three children (one 14-year-old and eight-year-old twin).

In the medical history form, the participant (EMCC) reported the complaints that led her to seek MB treatment including heavy menstrual flow, fatigue, abdominal pain, irritability, mood swings, and endometrial polyp, as well as a history of several surgeries, and not wishing to undergo another surgical procedure. She was not taking any medication and not undergoing any other form of treatment. The participant voluntarily underwent MB treatment. In her medical history, she reported events related to her health including surgery to remove five intestine polyps and two thyroid nodules. She also reported past surgery to remove gallbladder, a Bartholin's cyst, a Nuck canal cyst, an inguinal hernia, and two cesarean sections, as well as experiencing a spontaneous abortion. As a complementary examination, she presented a transvaginal pelvic ultrasound performed in August 2020 which described: "Nodular Image in the Endometrial Cavity Suggestive of Polyp".

The MB treatment was applied as described by Durán (2008). This methodology consists of a complete scanning of all points identified through kinesiological testing to identify the Resonant Biomagnetic Points (also called BMP) using magnets on specific anatomical points. The magnets were positioned in pairs on

the resonances identified in the scanning. The break of the charge polarization occurred in about 30 minutes.

In order when there is a pH imbalance in any anatomical structure, applying a scanning magnet (north pole) to specific locations of the body creates a change in bioelectricity. The bioelectrical changes are detected and interpreted by the cerebral amygdala which alters the bioelectricity of the brain and stimulates the left parietal region. As a result, the iliopsoas, popliteal, posterior tibial, and flexor digitorum longus muscles of the right leg contract causing shortening of the limb. The shortening of the right hemibody may be also called the magnetic sympathetic reflex of the foot, or simply, the Goiz reflex (Figure 1). This phenomenon occurs due to the interaction of the negative magnetic field with the bioelectric and biomagnetic charge created as a result of local pH changes (DURÁN, 2008; MARTÍNEZ, 2018; CASTEJÓN, 2015).

FIGURE 1: The right hemibody shortening

Source: BOSSA (2021a)

The left hemibody remains stable probably due to the influence of the electromagnetic field of the heart which polarizes and depolarizes the left hemibody after heartbeat. The alternation in electromagnetic waves produced by the heartbeat inhibits left shortening (DURÁN, 2008; MARTINEZ, 2018b; CASTEJÓN, 2015). Thus, the kinesiological test used as a bioenergetic reference for understanding and identifying BMP is clarified; where there is no imbalance, the right hemibody remains static as shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: Hemibody pairing

Source: BOSSA (2021a)

On May 23, 2021, a MB session was performed using the Basic Protocol (BP) (Table 1) followed by a complete scanning according to Bossa's protocol (2021a). The results are presented in Table 2 with a total duration of 01:05 hours. After a 21-day interval, a session of Magnetic Emotional Unblocking (MEU) was applied using the Psychic Complex (PC) for 40 minutes (Figure 3).

2.1. First session (May, 23th 2021) – Basic Protocol + complete scanning

The basic protocol is composed by a set of BMP which together provide organism detoxification regulating the bioelectric activity of the nervous, immunologic, digestive, and glandular systems (Table 1). Each BMP has a specific action (Table 2).

Table 1 – Basic Protocol

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BMP	North impaction point (-)	South impaction point (+)
BMP 1	Liver	Liver
BMP 2	Liver	Kidney (R)
BMP 3	Kidney (R/L)	Kidney (R/L)
BMP 4	Spinal Bulb	Lumbar ¾
BMP 5	Supra Spinosus (R/L)	Supra Spinosus (R/L)
BMP 6	Thymus	Rectum
BMP 7	Hip (R/L)	Hip (D/E)
BMP 8	Cardia	Appendix
BMP 9	Transverse colon	Liver
BMP 10	Thyroid (R/L)	Thyroid (R/L)
BMP 11	Vagina (R/L)	Vagina (CL)
BMP 12	Lumbar ¾	Kidney (R/L)

R - right; L - left; CL - contralateral. Source: BOSSA (2023).

Table 2: Basic Protocol – Functions

Biomagnetic Pair (BMP)	Functions in organism
Liver/Liver and Liver/Kidney	Detoxify the organism
Kidney / Kidney	Detoxify, produce muscle relaxation, relax the renal artery, promote diuresis and regulate blood pressure
Spinal Bulb /Lumbar ¾	Regularize the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems, relieve stress, improve glandular secretion, reduce muscle contraction, depolarize other BMP in the region, reduce recovery symptoms, improve drug effectiveness
Supra Spinosus/Supra Spinosus	Decrease tiredness and respiratory symptoms
Thymus/Rectum	Strengthen the immune system
Hip/Hip	Prevent joint wear, osteoporosis, and osteopenia
Cardia/Appendix and Transverse colon/Liver	Improve gastrointestinal activity
Thyroid/ Thyroid	Improve metabolism
Vagina/Vagina	Help to depolarize other BMP and minimize pelvic infections
Lumbar/Kidney	Avoid abscesses and infiltrates in the pelvic region

Source: (BOSSA, 2023; MARTÍNEZ, 2019)

Complete Scanning (BOSSA, 2021a) was performed where the BMP for treatment were identified. This identification is described in Table 3. In this case, the

magnets were applied for 20 minutes.

Table 3 – Biomagnetic pairs identified

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BMP	North impaction point (-)	South impaction point (+)
BMP 1	Pleura (R)	Peritoneum (L)
BMP 2	Scapula (R)	Scapula (L)
BMP 3	Elbow (R)	Elbow (L)
BMP 4	Pineal	Pineal
BMP 5	Pituitary	Pituitary
BMP 6	Ear (R)	Ear (L)
BMP 7	Mastoid (R)	Mastoid (L)
BMP 8	Parotid (R)	Parotid (L)
BMP 9	Descending Colon	Quadriceps (L)
BMP 10	Esophagus	Bladder
BMP 11	Urethral Sphincter Upp	Urethral Sphincter Low
BMP 12	Endometrium	Kidney (L)
PEP 13	Silvio's Fissure (R)	Silvio's Fissure (L)
PEP 14	Trachea (R)	Heart

BMP – Biomagnetic Pair; PEP – Psicoemocional Pair; R – right; L – left; Upp – upper; Low – lower. Source: The authors, 2021.

In the MB treatment, complete scanning is the gold standard exam because it customizes each care as it is performed to find the energetic dysfunctions that support the signs and symptoms of pathologies. Among the personalized BMP identified, dysfunctional, regular, psycho emotional BMP, and a special pair for flow drainage named “Trauma Pair” were found. The BMP that performed on gland balance were Pineal/Pineal; Pituitary/Pituitary, and Parotid/Parotid. The regular BMP that may be harboring some pathogenic microorganism such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, were the following: Pleura/Peritoneum; Scapula/Scapula; Elbow/Elbow; Ear/Ear; Mastoid/Mastoid; Descending Colon/Quadriceps; Esophagus/Bladder; Upper Urethral Sphincter/Lower Urethral

Sphincter. The psycho emotional pairs treat dysfunctions of areas related to the limbic and emotional system as Silvian Fissure/Silvian Fissure for lack of inspiration, and Trachea/Heart for intolerance (MARTÍNEZ, 2015; BOSSA 2023).

MB contemplates some special BMP that act at the tissue level stimulating the functioning of cells and tissues that make up specific systems. In the case of this study, the complete scanning leads to the Trauma Pair implementation also known as the anti-inflammatory and analgesic pair established in the Endometrium/Kidney L identified. This BMP was treated with magnets for 20 minutes during 20 days (interval of days until the next appointment).

2.2. Second session (June, 13th 2021) – Psychical complex (PC) + Magnetic Emotional Unblocking (MEU)

The participant reported feeling more disposed and having new life goals at the beginning of the second session. The PC (Figure 3) was initially applied. The PC is a protocol composed of 10 magnets used in conjunction with MEU. The PC aims to promote bioenergetic and biochemical adjustments for emotional balance and energy unblocking; it was used for 40 minutes. The MEU technique releases the vibrational and energetic resonance of emotions in the organs allowing the glands to harmonize each other and adjust the stress levels that negatively affect immune function. The emotions involved in this MEU session were ashamed, surprised, stripped, insecure, agonized, anxious, unhappy, offended, and vigilant.

FIGURE 3: Psychical complex

The image illustrates the magnets applied to anatomical points composing the Psychological Complex. The red color represents the north pole of the magnet in contact with the skin. The black color represents the south pole. D: right hemisphere; E: left hemisphere. Description of the PC points: the Prefrontal Cortex (D) stimulates, strengthens, and activates circulation. The center of the Frontal Cortex (E) relaxes, establishing a neuronal connection of emotions or traumas and facilitating the excretion of biochemical substances into the bloodstream. The Prefrontal Cortex (E) relaxes the rational area to allow emotions to flow. The Parietal (E) stimulates the area for receiving and processing sensory information from the body, helping the frontal cortex interpret bodily reactions. The Parietal (D) relaxes the area for receiving and processing sensory information from the body to allow the release of emotions from the subconscious. The base of the posterior cerebellum (D) stimulates the cerebellum to release emotional memories. The palm (D/E) promotes relaxation. The patella (D/E) helps to release fears.

After the sessions, the participant reported improvement and remission of all symptoms. A new transvaginal pelvic ultrasound exam was performed on July 1st,

2021, with the conclusion report: Uterus and Ovaries with normal ultrasound pattern showing absence of EP.

3. DISCUSSION

At the beginning of the treatment including MB the participant reported intense menstrual flow, low mood, abdominal pain, excessive tiredness, irritability, and mood swings. Following the sessions, the participant reported feeling very energized and transformed with goals and a new purpose in life. After these sessions, the participant presented a report showing an absence of pelvic endometriosis (EP). This suggests that Biomagnetic Pair Therapy together with Magnetic Emotional Unblocking have a beneficial effect not only in treating EP but also in alleviating other signs and symptoms presented by the volunteer.

Regarding the effect of MB, Frank (2017) has found beneficial effects on *Salmonella typhi* (typhoid fever) treatment. This study only evaluated the response to treatment with MB without any allopathic treatment provided by medicine or another similar field. Ten out of 13 participants tested negative in serological tests after MB isolated MB treatment also reporting clinical and symptomatic improvement. Meanwhile, Damyanov et al. 's (2019a), Damyanov et al.'s (2019b) and Martini et al.'s (2023) studies on cancer treatment showed clinical remission after sessions of MB together with conventional treatments. In our study, we obtained complete clinical remission of EP and other symptoms in two sessions demonstrating the potential beneficial effect of MB in conjunction with MEU.

EP is characterized by tissue dysfunction affecting estrogen and progesterone receptors which are more abundant in the glandular epithelium (NIJKANG et al., 2019). It demonstrates glandular bioenergetic alterations and direct effects on systems. MB directly regulates bioelectrical alterations by depolarizing biomagnetic pairs. Thus, the technique has the potential to act in the negatively entropic way in order to normalize organic functions and restore tissue health (DURÁN, 2014).

There is a risk of EP progressing to a neoplastic condition during gynecological monitoring. Therefore, the present study demonstrates that MB together with MEU may be an alternative treatment for polyps and cancer prevention. BMP therapy has been shown to be relevant in cancer treatment. It may be possible due to Isaac Goiz Durán methodology consisting on aspects of integrative oncology; it defines the influence of human microbiota as a determinant factor in tumor growth (DURÁN, 2008; DAMYANOV et al., 2019a; DAMYANOV et al., 2019b; MARTINI *et al.*, 2023).

Studies reporting the effects of MB on the treatment of diseases are still scarce while studies using MEU do not exist. Therefore, it is necessary that more investigations on these techniques are necessary. A consolidated literature on case reports may guide more in-depth studies, such as controlled, randomized, double-blind clinical trials.

4. CONCLUSION

It is necessary to invest in scientific research on both MB and MEU due to be non-invasive, painless, easy to apply, and low-cost techniques. In addition, these techniques may be accessible providing several possibilities for applicability in some pathology. Thus, it becomes possible to establish them as complementary treatments since the scientific evidence helps this field to clarify concepts and applications. The scientific knowledge in MB would assist conventional medicine in public health care.

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